

A New Pterocarpin Glycoside from *Trifolium pratense*

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TRIFOLIUM pratense (N.O. Leguminosae) is native from Kashmir to Garhwal, and is reported to be used as expectorant and also as an important ingredient for the treatment of ulcers. The present communication reports the isolation of maackianin 3-O- β -D-galactopyranoside from its roots.

The powdered, dried roots of *T. pratense* were extracted with methanol and the concentrated extract was worked up by column chromatography to get colourless needles, m.p. 153–55°, C₂₂H₂₂O₁₀, M⁺ 446; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 273, 286 and 307 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 410, 1 720, 1 610, 1 585 and 1 500 cm⁻¹; δ 7.32, 6.63, 6.66, 6.35, 5.88, 5.43, 4.65, 3.72, 4.30, 4.42–4.5, 2.02, 2.05, 1.97 and 2.12.

On acid hydrolysis in dioxane–water², it yielded D-galactose (co-pc and tlc) and an aglycone which crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 180–82°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆, M⁺ 284; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 218, 282 and 290 nm, λ_{\max} (EtOH) 208, 236 and 285 nm, λ_{\max} (EtOH+NaOH) 221, 255, 280 and 306 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 710, 1 620, 1 590, 1 385, 1 355, 1 290, 1 180, 1 150, 1 035, 850, 830 and 790 cm⁻¹; δ 7.32 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₁-H), 6.63 (2H, m, C₇, C₈-H), 6.66 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, C₄-H), 6.35 (1H, s, C₁₀-H), 5.88 (2H, d, J 1 Hz, OCH₂O), 5.43 (1H, m, C₁₁ α -H), 4.05 (1H, q, C₆ α -H) and 3.72 (2H, m, C₆-H).

From physical and spectral data, the aglycone was identified as maackianin. Its identify was further confirmed by its conversion to acetyl derivative³, m.p. 179°, [α]_D²⁰ –176°.

Periodate oxidation⁴ and enzymatic hydrolysis⁵ indicated that the glycoside was made up of one mole of aglycone and one mol of sugar and having β -linkage. Absence of peak at λ_{\max} (EtOH+NaOH) 255 in the uv spectra of the glycoside confirmed that the C₈-OH of pterocarpin was involved in glycosylation⁶. Permethylation⁷ of the glycoside showed that the C₁-OH of galactose was involved in glycoside linkage. Thus the glycoside was identified as maackianin 3-O- β -D-galactopyranoside.

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Chemical Investigation of *Echinops echinatus*

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THE medicinal uses¹⁻³ of the roots of *Echinops echinatus* (Fam. Compositae) prompted us to undertake the investigation on the roots of the plant wherefrom we have isolated ω -methylallophanic acid and allophanic acid.

The ethanolic extract of the air-dried powdered roots (5 kg) was methylated with diazomethane in ether. The methylated ethanol extract was separated on silica gel column using different solvents and their mixtures as eluents.

From the benzene eluate of the methylated ethanolic extract, a compound obtained was recrystallised from methanol as pinkish needles, m.p. 163°, C₄H₈N₂O₃; ν_{\max} 3 415–3 310 (NH), 1 750–1 720 (N–COOCH₃), 1 690, 1 560–1 510 cm⁻¹ (HN–CO–NH); δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃), 2.81 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, HNCCH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, CO–OCH₃), 7.85 (1H, s, H₃C–NH) and 9.12 (1H, s, HN–CO)(D₂O exchangeable); m/z 132 (M⁺ 46%), 117(3.8%), 101(3.0%), 74(17.0%) and (24.0%). The compound was identified as ω -methylallophanic acid (as methyl ester, 1, lit.⁴ m.p. 163.5° as methyl ester).

The methanol eluate of the methylated ethanolic extract yielded a compound which was recrystallised from benzene as colourless crystals, m.p. 207–09°d, C₉H₈N₂O₃, soluble in benzene and chloroform; ν_{\max} 3 420–3 260 (NH), 2 980–2 920, 1 760–1 745 (N–COOCH₃) and 1 590–1 550 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃), 3.7 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 7.2 (2H, s,

NH₂) and 9.9 (1H, s, NH)(D₂O exchangeable); *m/z* 118 (*M*⁺ 13.7%), 87 (4.0%), 76 (30.8%), 75 (75.0%), 70 (2.8%) and 59 (7.8%). The compound was identified as aliphatic acid (as methyl ester, 2, lit.⁹ m.p. 208°d as methyl ester).

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Extractive AAS Determination of Lead

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THE present paper describes a method for selective and quantitative extraction of trace quantities of lead by the liquid chelating exchanger (LCE), trifluoroacetylacetone type (RCOCH₂COCF₃) in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline (phen.) using chloroform as diluent and its subsequent determination by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). The method has been successfully applied to determine lead content in alloy containing phosphorus.

Experimental

LCE (RCOCH₂COCF₃; R=C₉H₁₉) from Versatic-10 was prepared following the procedure described earlier^{1,2}. A 0.1 *M* solution of LCE in ethanol was used in the present work. A stock solution of lead(II) was prepared by dissolving Pb(CH₃COO)₂·3H₂O (Sarabhai Merck) in double-distilled water and was standardised complexometrically³. All the other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer maintaining the following conditions: lead hollow cathode lamp current, 7 mA; burner height, 5 mm; wavelength, 217.0 nm; slit width, 1.9 Å; air flow rate, 10 dm³ min⁻¹; acetylene flow rate, 2.6 dm³ min⁻¹; optimum working range, 5–20 ppm. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

Procedure: To a solution of lead (100 mg dm⁻³) in a 50 ml separatory funnel, dilute ammonia was added to adjust the pH to ~7.0, tris-buffer solution (2 ml; pH=7.2) was then added and the total volume of the solution was made up to 10 ml. To it each of the 0.1 *M* chelating exchanger (1 ml) and 0.03 *M* phen. were added and the mixture was shaken. Then chloroform (5 ml) was added, shaken and allowed to settle for 5 min. The organic phase was taken into another separatory funnel and the aqueous phase was washed with chloroform (2×2 ml) and taken in the same separatory funnel. The resulting solution was stripped back into 0.1 *N* HNO₃. The aqueous phase was taken and volume was made up to 10 ml. The absorbance value of the resulting solution was measured on the AAS and the amount of lead was found out from the calibration curve.

The method was applied for the determination of lead in different alloy samples obtained from the Bureau of Analysed Samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF LEAD IN ALLOY^a SAMPLES

Description of alloy constituent (%)	Lead ^b found	
	Direct AAS	Present method
Gun metal (6 g): Cu (86.4), Zn (1.3), Sn (10.5), Pb (1.02)	1.015 ±0.010	1.019 ±0.014
H.T. Brass (10 g): Cu (60.8), Zn (32.0), Fe (1.56), Al (3.34), Mn (1.36), Pb (0.23)	0.229 ±0.003	0.231 ±0.002
Phosphor bronze (7 g): Cu (88.4), Sn (10.1), P (1.31), Pb (0.02)	c	0.021 ±0.0002

^aFrom Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Middlesbrough, Cleveland, U.S.A., August 1975. ^bAverage of three determinations. ^cCan not be determined.

Results and Discussion

Lead was quantitatively extracted from aqueous medium in the pH range 6.6–9.0. Quantitative extraction of lead was achieved with chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, tributyl phosphate and benzene; the percentage of extraction being 100 in each solvent. Other solvents, viz., 1,2-dichloroethane (90.0%), cyclohexane (56.7%) and methyl isobutyl ketone (46.7%) were also used. Concentration of LCE varied from 0.075 to 0.600 *M* in chloroform, 0.1 *M* LCE solution was sufficient, and the excess amount did not affect the extraction of lead. Extraction was increased with increasing phen.